

DNA content in rice hybrids and heterosis

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Certain metabolic functions in the nucleus are enhanced in heterotic plants compared with those of their parents. However, what happens to the nucleus under heterozygosity is still unknown. Nebiolo et al (1983), in a study on RNA metabolism in protoplasts isolated from seedlings of a heterotic maize hybrid and its parents, suggested that a hybrid nucleus may provide advantages in the rate of DNA and RNA synthesis. We studied the nuclear behavior and DNA content in hybrids to improve understanding of the molecular basis of heterosis.

Using a MIPS-1 imaging analytical instrument with analytical software, intact

nuclei were isolated from root tips on slides, stained with Feulgen, and screened for different mitotic stages (prophase, metaphase, anaphase, and telophase). Screened nuclei were synchronically determined based on optic density (OD), integrated optic density (IOD), and size.

We selected five female indica parental lines, six male indica parental lines, and nine hybrids derived from them. We examined 4,401 nuclei from root tips based on OD, IOD, and nucleus size (or an av of 55 nuclei for each mitotic stage for each material). Average OD value of nuclei from the nine hybrids was less than that from the 11 parental lines. However, average IOD value was greater in hybrids than in the parents (see table). Average nucleus size, which significantly expanded during prophase and telophase stages (at the 5% level), was greater in the hybrids. OD, IOD, and nucleus size were compared for hybrids and their parents (see figure). We found that nucleus size is directly proportional to IOD based on the regres-

sion index of about 0.977. Increases in DNA content and nucleus size and decrease in DNA density occurring in the hybrids indicate that gene expression is probably enhanced. These factors could be important for understanding karyological and molecular bases of rice heterosis. However, we have not yet determined which part of the DNA increases and what its functions are. ■

Variation in DNA content and nuclear size in hybrids compared with those in their parental lines (represented at zero).

Comparison of nuclear size and DNA content between nine hybrids and their parental lines.

Determinant ^a	Prophase ^b			Metaphase			Anaphase			Telophase		
	F	M	H	F	M	H	F	M	H	F	M	H
Nuclei (no.)	333	374	592	143	218	298	254	313	406	316	416	738
OD (arbitrary)	0.158	0.157	0.146	0.300	0.286	0.283	0.240	0.239	0.231	0.176	0.176	0.170
IOD (arbitrary)	5.69	5.87	6.22	3.89	3.98	4.04	2.19	2.18	2.27	2.5	2.56	2.73
Size (μm^2)	36.77	38.38	43.41*	13.25	14.09	14.56	9.38	9.29	10.16	14.67	14.91	17*

^aOD = optic density, IOD = integrated optic density. ^bF = female line, M = male line, H = hybrid. * = significant at the 5% level.

Induction of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens vir* genes by rice

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Transformation of monocotyledonous plants, such as rice, by *Agrobacterium* has low efficiency and has not yet become a routine laboratory technique. We studied whether rice tissues have limited ability to induce *Agrobacterium vir* genes and to promote synthesis of T-strands.

We used *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain A348 harboring a cosmid with *virE-lacZ* fusion to monitor ability of plant tissues to induce *vir* genes. Tobacco leaf segments preincubated for 48 h in Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium and incubated with *Agrobacterium* for 24 h induced *virE* expression to 4,500 Miller units, which equaled *vir* induction level obtained using the chemical signal, acetosyringone. Induction of *virE* expression by leaf segments of *Oryza sativa* L. cv Co 43 was low (only about 5% of that achieved by tobacco leaf segments).

We analyzed various parts of rice seedlings of different ages for their ability to induce *vir* genes. Rice roots, leaf bases,

coleoptiles, and leaf segments induced *vir* genes to very low levels (see table). Only scutellum from 4-d-old seedlings induced *virE* to a high level (about 40% of induction by tobacco). We found that a 72-h preincubation is essential for *vir* gene induction. Most of the *vir* gene induction was associated with the preincubated scutellum per se. The conditioned medium exhibited very little induction.

Agrobacterium efficiently transformed scutellum-derived calli of japonica rice cultured for 25 d on a 2,4-D-containing medium (Hiei et al 1994). However, scutella excised from 5-d-old seedlings and grown on 2,4-D-containing medium were transformed at very low efficiency.

Induction of *A. tumefaciens virE* gene by various parts of rice plants of different ages.

Age of rice plant (d)	Part of rice plant preincubated for 72 h	Mean Miller units ± SE
4	Coleoptile	203 ± 4
	Scutellum	2919 ± 284
8	Leaf blade	501 ± 47
	Leaf base	378 ± 42
	Root	362 ± 39
14	Leaf blade	353 ± 17
	Leaf base	531 ± 22
20	Leaf blade	528 ± 75
	Leaf base	455 ± 15
Control values:	MS medium	- 175 ± 8
	MS medium + 60 μM AS	-5129 ± 90
	MS medium + tobacco leaf segments	-6840 ± 235

Scutellum-derived calli induced *vir E* expression to 1,745 Miller units, whereas scutella excised from 5-d-old seedlings and grown on 2,4-D-containing medium

induced *virE* only to about 646 Miller units. The scutellum-derived calli that induced *vir* genes more efficiently exhibited a higher level of susceptibility to *Agrobacterium* mediated transformation.

However, scutella excised from 4-d-old seedlings and grown on hormone-free medium induced *vir* gene expression to a level (2,547 Miller units) higher than that achieved with scutellum-derived calli. The results suggest that these scutella may be more susceptible to *Agrobacterium* than the scutellum-derived calli. We also found that rice scutellum promotes generation of the T-DNA transfer intermediates, T-strands, in *Agrobacterium*.

Cited references

Hiei Y, Ohta S, Komari T, Kumashiro T. 1994. Efficient transformation of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) mediated by *Agrobacterium* and sequence analysis of the boundaries of the T-DNA. *Plant J.* 6:271-282. ■

each other. A 0.52-kb *EcoRI/XhoI* fragment of a cDNA clone (RTS1) was used as a probe for screening the IR54 genomic library. A positive genomic clone (RTS2) was isolated and sequenced. Northern blot analysis (Fig. 1) and in situ hybridization (Fig. 2) showed that the gene was predominantly expressed in the anther's tapetum during vigorous meiosis and disappeared before anthesis. Sequence comparison between the cDNA clone

1. Northern blot of total RNA isolated from leaves, seeds, and panicles at various development stages and probed with putative anther-specific cDNA. Lanes with RNA are (A) leaf, (B) panicle, 4 d before C, (C) panicle when auricles of first and second leaves are at same level, (D) panicle, 4 d after C, (E) panicle, 8 d after C, (F) panicle, 12 d after C, and (G) seed.

Isolation of a tapetum-specific gene and promoter from rice

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Potential vulnerability of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS)-derived hybrids calls for developing an alternative method of controlling male fertility/sterility for rice breeding and hybrid development. A tapetal-specific promoter-driving barnase induced sterility in tobacco and oil seed rape plants (Mariani et al 1992). Fertility was restored with the same promoter-driving barstar. Although tapetum-specific cDNA clones have recently been isolated from rice (Tsuchiya et al 1992) no regulating sequences have been reported. Developing a system by which male fertility in rice can be controlled requires a promoter that can regulate gene expression, specifically in the male organ, during anther development.

We cloned a rice anther (tapetum)-specific cDNA and corresponding genomic

DNA from rice cultivar IR54. A panicle cDNA library was constructed and differentially screened for panicle and anther specificity. We selected two cDNA clones that could be cross-hybridized with

2. In situ hybridization of transverse sections through rice spikelet, including anthers with denatured cDNA (RTS1) probe. Spikelets were sampled when auricle of first leaf was 2.5 cm above the auricle of the second leaf. (A) and (B) anthers and glumes; (C) lower magnification of A; (D) and (E) RNase-treated anthers before hybridization; and (F) leaf sheath, a = anther; t = tapetum; lo = locule; g = glume; ep = epidermis; and en = endothecium.

